

Group IV binary carbides with double layer honeycomb lattice structure

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Abstract:

We explore the possibility of SiC, GeC, and SnC to form 2D structures, using evolutionary structure prediction tools and first-principles calculations. For SiC, a double layer honeycomb structure has the lowest energy, while GeC and SnC adopt other structures due to atomic size mismatch. The double layer honeycomb structure of SiC has a moderately large exfoliation energy, and covalent interlayer bonding that results in a stiff structure and high frequency phonons. Electronically, we find the double-layer SiC to be a semiconductor with an indirect band gap in the visible spectral range. Finally, we explore stacked heterojunctions with graphene to illustrate how double layer SiC could be integrated with existing materials.

1. Introduction

The discovery of graphene, a single-layer carbon sheet derived from graphite, has greatly propelled the investigation of two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials. This research is motivated by the outstanding features of such 2D materials, including mechanical flexibility, nearly perfect optical transparency, high thermal conductivity, and high carrier mobility^{1,2}. Electronically, graphene with a Dirac cone dispersion lacks a band gap, which significantly limits its applications in optoelectronic nanodevices. Therefore, researchers have explored other inorganic 2D nanomaterials, beyond graphene^{3,4}, and elemental group-IV monolayer materials, commonly known as group-IV xenes, are particularly interesting. These include semimetals such as stanene⁵, germanene^{6,7}, and silicene^{8,9} that show behavior akin to massless Dirac fermions analogous to graphene. In contrast to the flat lattice of graphene, group-IV xenes can exhibit a buckled configuration, which enables an opening of a band gap when exposed to a vertical electric field^{10,11}.

Group-IV carbides are being actively studied and new allotropes with unique properties are continually unveiled. For example, 2D tetrahexagonal group-IV carbides incorporating C₂ dimers (th-SiC₂, th-GeC₂, and th-SnC₂) were recently introduced. These structures exhibit robust structural stability, a direct band gap, and anisotropic high carrier mobility, making them promising for applications in electronics¹². X. Li et al.¹³ reported the presence of stable pentagonal silicon carbide (P-SiC₂) and showed its promising potential for photocatalytic water splitting. M. E. Kilic et al.¹⁴ reported the existence of pentagonal group-IV binary and ternary carbides and showed that th-SiC₂ can be precisely formed by applying the Stone-Wales (SW)

transformation to penta-SiC₂. Beyond penta-SiC₂, the predicted th-XC₂ carbides suggest the potential existence of other 2D penta-carbides.

However, single-layer buckled honeycomb structures made from traditional semiconductors are often not stable, which stimulates research interest in other approaches to stabilize conventional semiconductors in their 2D form. For example, in 2018, Lucking et al. predicted a 2D structure known as the double-layer honeycomb (DLHC) lattice¹⁵. This structure should have lower formation energy than the truncated bulk and other 2D counterparts, such as in InAs¹⁶, AlSb^{17,18}, and CdTe^{19,20}. Later, several such 2D materials were successfully fabricated experimentally²¹⁻²⁴. The DLHC configuration introduces a novel method for obtaining 2D materials from conventional 3D semiconductors, including group I-VII, II-VI, and III-V compounds. Especially challenging is the realization of I-VII 2D materials through intermediate configurations that differ from the DLHC structure. Therefore, DLHC materials not only broaden the spectrum of 2D materials, but being double-layered, these structures promise to be more rigid against wobbling and flexing than their single-layer counterparts and may possess distinct electronic and optical properties (as double-layer graphene does). Recent advances in the experimental fabrication of DLHC materials, defect engineering, chemical and optical properties are covered in ref.²⁵

Taking motivation from recent fabrication of high-quality honeycomb systems^{18,26} based on SiC, AlSb, and InSb, we explore a new series of group-IV carbides, XC, with X=Si, Ge, Sn. We use the combination of evolutionary structure prediction and density functional theory (DFT) to find lowest-energy structures, which leads us to identify the DLHC structure for SiC. We calculate the mechanical, electronic and optical properties of DLHC SiC and discuss possible applications.

2. Computational Methods

We used DFT in the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP)^{27,28} to investigate the structural, electronic, and mechanical properties of single- and double-layer XC (X=Si, Ge, Sn) crystals and the plane-wave projector-augmented wave method (PAW)²⁹ with Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional³⁰. To get more precise band gaps, we also performed electronic structure calculations with was further improved by incorporating Heyd–Scuseria–Ernzerhof functional (HSE06)³¹. The Bader technique was utilized to determine the charge transfer between atoms³² and the DFT-D2 approach of Grimme to include van der Waals interactions (vdW)³³. A plane wave kinetic energy cutoff of 520 eV was used for DLHC structures. Gaussian broadening of 0.05 eV was used for electronic occupations, and a 20 Å vacuum space was included to separate the layers in the perpendicular direction. The total energy was converged to 10⁻⁵ eV and 10⁻⁴ eV for electronic and individual ionic steps, respectively, and Γ centered k-point meshes of 11×11×1 and 21×21×1 were taken for structural optimization and optical property calculations. Geometric relaxation of atoms within the primitive cell was applied until all stress tensor components dropped below 1 kbar. Phonon dispersion was obtained with the PHON code implementing finite difference method³⁴. Finally, the cohesive energy per formula unit was calculated as $E_{\text{coh}} = \frac{1}{4}(E_{\text{tot}} - 2E_X - 2E_C)$, where E_X and E_C are the energies of isolated group-IV (X= Si, Ge, and Sn) atoms and C atom, respectively. E_{tot} denotes the total energy of the XC layer and the factors of two and four account for the number of X and C atoms and total atoms constituting the primitive unit cell, respectively. By this definition, a lower value of E_{coh} identifies a more energetically (or thermodynamically) stable structure. We calculated the cohesive energy of DLHC-SiC to be 6.05 eV per atom, closely aligning with the previously reported value of 6.07 eV per atom³⁵ for single-layer SiC (see Table S1 in the Supporting Information). In the case of GeC, the cohesive energy per atom was 5.42 eV per atom, and for DLHC-SnC 4.93 eV per atom. These

values are lower than those of single layers, as detailed in Table S1. Furthermore, the cohesive energies of XC structures based on the most abundant elemental form of the atoms were calculated and are also reported in Table S1. These values are significantly larger than previously reported in the theoretical prediction of 2D carbon monochalcogenides.³⁶

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Evolutionary structure search

Structure prediction is one of the most difficult problems due to a multitude of competing structures. Here we used an evolutionary structure prediction algorithm as implemented in the USPEX code³⁷⁻³⁹ to screen possible structures with 1:1 XC stoichiometry. In order to restrict the algorithm to 2D layered structures, we have set the maximum thickness for structures of interest to 3 Å with an interlayer distance of 20 Å. A minimum of 2 and a maximum of 8 atoms were allowed per unit cell for all possible structures. The candidate structures are described in Table I for all three different X. Our *ab-initio* structure prediction as reported in Table I shows that SiC accommodates a DLHC structure, which is at least 0.2 meV lower in energy than its P1 counterpart without any symmetry. Other metastable structures are reported in the Supplementary information, where we compare their energy with the hexagonal SiC bulk reference, refined from X-ray data by Mesquita⁴⁰. The DLHC energy, upon inclusion of DFT-D2 vdW interactions³³, was found to be 0.62 eV/formula unit higher than the experimental bulk SiC form. However, the case is quite different for the other two compounds. For GeC and SnC, the corresponding DLHC structures are much higher in energy (>0.5 and >1.3 eV, respectively, as compared to their low-symmetry structures), and the algorithm fails to find them without increasing the number of generations or using the SiC structure as an initial seed. In fact, the structural forms of both these cases appear phase-segregated, and hence, their DLHC structures are presumed to be highly metastable.

3.2. Exfoliability of the predicted DLHC binary carbides

For the 2D DLHC structure of SiC, we examine whether this material can be synthesized via exfoliation techniques. Mounet and co-workers⁴¹ performed a high-throughput density-functional theory-based exfoliation feasibility test for many known compounds. Here we employ their methodology to test whether the structures we found can be obtained via exfoliation technique starting from their bulk parents. We calculated binding energies using DFT-d2 approximation to include vdW interaction. In Fig. 2, we show a comparison of these binding energies for a few known 2D materials that can be produced using exfoliation. We obtained an exfoliation energy of about 143 meV/Å² for DLHC SiC. In comparison, graphene exfoliation energy was found to only 20.3 meV/Å².⁴¹

Figure 1. Lowest energy structures as predicted by the evolutionary search algorithm for all three materials: (a-b) SiC, (c) GeC and (d) SnC. For SiC, we have a trigonal crystal in its double layered honeycomb structure. However, for both GeC and SnC, low symmetry monoclinic cells are obtained. Ge ions tend to form long 1D chains with honeycomb C rings. In SnC, both Sn and C atoms form intercalated zigzag chains.

Table I. Possible structures of the XC (X=Si, Ge, Sn) compounds as predicted by the evolutionary algorithm, arranged in decreasing order of energetic stability, with respect to their corresponding X-DLHC structure. The number of formula units per unit cell and the calculated enthalpy per unit of XC have been shown too. The * marks the DLHC structure. Note that only in the case of Si, the DLHC structure possesses the lowest energy.

Species	Symmetry	Formula Unit/Cell	Enthalpy/f.u. (eV/XC)
SiC	$P\bar{3}m1$ (164) *	2	0.000
	Cm (8)	2	+0.124
	P1 (1)	2	+0.157
	$Pmn2_1$ (31)	4	+0.306
	$P3m1$ (156)	3	+0.573
GeC	P1 (1)	4	-0.510
	Pmma (51)	2	-0.506
	$P\bar{1}$ (2)	2	-0.492
	Pmna (53)	4	-0.138
	$P\bar{3}m1$ (164) *	2	0.000
SnC	Pmma (51)	2	-1.399
	$P\bar{1}$ (2)	4	-1.197
	$P\bar{3}m1$ (164) *	2	0.000

Figure 2. The exfoliation energies of a few known 2D materials are presented in comparison to our calculated SiC in its 2D DLHC structure on a log scale. The values are in units of $\text{meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ per layer. For materials with multiple known 2D forms, the symmetry space group is shown. The color indicates the ease

of exfoliability, with easily exfoliable materials ($E < 20 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$) in blue, potentially exfoliable ($20 < E < 105 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$) in green, and materials with higher exfoliation energy in yellow⁴¹.

3.3. Structural Properties

The DLHC- XC structures are shown in Figure 3. The crystal structure of SiC has space group $P\bar{3}m1$ (#164 in International Tables). The predicted lattice constants, X -C bond length d , and interlayer distance h are summarized in Table II. The energy of the SiC DLHC per formula unit is lower than that of a monolayer truncated from the bulk counterpart, but higher than that of bulk SiC. The electronic stability of DLHC structures originates from the replacement of dangling bonds through covalent interlayer interaction. To understand the nature of bonding we show the electron localization function for the DLHC structure of SiC as well as for fictitious GeC and SnC DLHC structures in Figure 3c. GeC and SnC have different lowest-energy structures, as shown in Table I and Fig. 1, and the DLHC structure for them is only used to illustrate bonding. In-plane π and σ bonds and out-of-plane π bonds can be identified. The layers within DLHC structures are covalently bound, with electrons from Si atoms facilitating the interlayer bonds. We implemented charge density difference (CDD) calculations, to examine the charge distribution in the studied DLHC- XC structures and show the charge difference between DLHC and densities from two separate single-layer calculations in Figure 3d. Here the charge density difference is the difference between the charge accumulation and depletion of the interacting double-layered SiC and SnC structures and that of the non-interacting bilayer GeC structures. As shown in Figure 3d, there are strong charge density differences at the interface between the DLHC-SiC and DLHC-SnC structures, representing a strong interaction, similar to a covalent bond. On the other hand, the lack of charge density differences between the bilayer-GeC sheets points to a weak vdW interaction and physisorption.

Figure 3. The atomic structure of SiC is shown in the (a) in-plane and (b) out-of-plane directions. c) Electron localization function (ELF) analysis reveals covalent interlayer bonding in SiC and SnC, and

vanishing interlayer ELF for GeC. The color scale shows the normalized ELF. (d) Charge density differences for the three structures with the isosurfaces at ± 0.003 a.u. for all three materials. The yellow region implies a charge surplus, while the cyan region corresponds to a charge depletion.

Table II. Calculated parameters for SiC and fictitious GeC and SnC DLHC structures: optimized in-plane lattice constants ($a = b$), in-plane and out-of-plane bond length between a carbon ion and X ions, d_{X-C} and h , respectively, the $X-C-X$ bond angle (θ), donated electron count per X atom (ρ_{X-C}), cohesive energy per atom (E_c), work function (Φ), band gaps E_g calculated within GGA, and within HSE06 on top of GGA.

Structure	a (Å)	d_{X-C} (Å)	h (Å)	θ_{C-X-C} (deg)	θ_{X-C-X} (deg)	E_{cohesive} (eV/atom)	$\Delta\rho_{(X-C)}$ (e^-)	Φ (eV)	E_{GGA} (eV)	$E_{\text{GGA+HSE}}$ (eV)
SiC	3.15	1.82	2.16	95.00	85.00	6.05	2.62	5.06	1.8	2.7
GeC	3.26	1.88	3.23	90.94	89.05	5.42	1.38	4.73	1.8	2.52
SnC	3.73	2.15	2.42	88.17	91.82	4.93	1.32	3.82	0.5	1.32

3.4. Mechanical properties

The calculated phonon dispersion of the SiC DLHC structures is reported in Figure S2. Phonons are stable across the entire Brillouin zone, indicating its dynamical stability. The phonon bandwidth is 509 cm^{-1} , and we obtained a phonon band gap from about 150 cm^{-1} to 350 cm^{-1} which makes this structure suitable for phononic devices, including phonon filters, cavities, waveguides, and more.

To explore the mechanical properties and the related stability, and stiffness of our materials, we calculated the elastic constants. The mechanical stability was tested using the elastic stability criteria⁴², specifically $C_{66} > 0$ and $C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2 > 0$, where C_{ij} are the in-plane elastic stiffness constants. The corresponding elastic constants were calculated by computing the stress resulting from the application of $\pm 1\%$ strain within the harmonic approximation. The energy change per unit area, $U_s(\epsilon)$, associated with strain in the XC layers is calculated as follows:

$$U_s(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{2}C_{11}\epsilon_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}C_{22}\epsilon_2^2 + C_{12}\epsilon_1\epsilon_2 + \frac{1}{2}C_{66}\epsilon_6^2, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_1, ϵ_2 correspond to uniaxial strain along x and y axes, ϵ_6 – to shear strain. $C_{11} = C_{22}$, $C_{66} = \frac{C_{11} - C_{12}}{2}$, in Voigt notation. The obtained elastic constants satisfy the elastic stability criteria (Table III) and confirm the mechanical stability of XC double layers.

The mechanical properties of 2D compounds allow to predict their response under the application of load. The linear elastic properties of 2D compounds can be described with the Poisson ratio, ν , which is the ratio of the transverse contraction strain to the longitudinal extension, and the in-plane stiffness, C , which is a measure of the rigidity of a material. Using the elastic constants that we obtained, we calculated the angular-dependent Poisson's ratio $\nu(\theta)$ and Young's modulus $Y(\theta)$ of XC double layers following ref.⁴³.

The Poisson ratio and in-plane stiffness, which are isotropic in the DLHC structures due to 3-fold symmetry, are listed in Table III, and their comparison to other materials is plotted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Comparison of the bulk moduli values for some well-known 2D materials in N/m . Panel (a) shows the Young's modulus values for tetrahexagonal SiC₂, GeC₂¹³, hexagonal-GeC⁴⁴, -SnC⁴⁵, hexagonal boron-nitride (h-BN)⁴⁶, graphene^{43,47}, S-SiC⁴⁸, TaS₂⁴⁹ and MoS₂⁵⁰. Our predicted DLHC/bilayer structures for SiC/GeC appear on the far right of both scales indicating very high bulk moduli values, if the structure is found stable.

The Poisson ratio is 0.22 for DLHC-SiC, which is comparable to graphene (0.16), h-BN (0.14), and single-layer SiC (S-SiC) (0.17). The Poisson ratio of DLHC-SiC relates to a high sensitivity to external loads, which is advantageous for applications in nanoelasticity. Both the Poisson ratio and Young's modulus of the XC structures are isotropic as shown in Figure S4.

Table III. Calculated elastic constant C_{ij} , in-plane stiffness C , Poisson's ratio, Young's modulus, Ultimate tensile strain UTS_x , UTS_y , UTS_{xy} .

Structure	C_{11} (N/m)	C_{12} (N/m)	C_{66} (N/m)	C	ν (N/m)	Y (N/m)	UTS_x GPa	UTS_y GPa	UTS_{xy} GPa
SiC	232.67	52.96	89.86	571.23	0.22	220.62	20	20	19
GeC	310.94	103.25	103.85	828.34	0.33	276.66	---	---	---
SnC	109.98	35.65	37.85	291.26	0.32	98.42	20	20	13

3.5. Electronic and Optical Properties

Figure 5 displays the electronic band structures calculated with PBE and HSE06 exchange correlation functionals^{30,31}. DLHC SiC is a semiconductor with indirect bandgap of 1.8 eV from PBE and 2.7 eV from HSE functional calculations³¹. This difference originates from a band gap underestimation by PBE³⁰. The conduction band minimum (CBM) is at the M point, and the valence band maximum (VBM) is located between the K and Γ points. Table II summarizes the band gaps obtained from PBE and HSE06 calculations, including the values obtained for GeC and SnC in DLHC structure for completeness (the results of the electronic structure calculations for GeC and SnC double layer structures are displayed in Figure S4). The projected density of states, shown in Fig 5a, reveals that the lowest conduction band originates from the p_z orbitals of C atoms, while the VBM stems from the s orbital. The projected density of states, shown in Fig. 5a, reveals that the lowest conduction band originates from the mixing of p_z orbitals of C atoms and s orbitals of Si, while the VBM stems from the p_z orbital of C atoms. Figure 5c shows the effect of compressive and tensile strains up to 5% on the band gap, indicating a strong tunability of the band gap by mechanical distortions.

Figure 5. Electronic properties of DLHC-SiC. (a) DLHC SiC band structure. Red dashed and black solid lines are computed with HSE06 and PBE, respectively. The total and X- and C-projected density of states is shown by black, red, and blue lines. (b) VBM and CBM charge distribution. (c) Bandgap energy calculated for biaxial ($\epsilon_{xx}+\epsilon_{yy}$), uniaxial strains in the armchair (ϵ_{xx} , blue) and Zigzag (ϵ_{yy} , green) forms up to +/- 5%.

4. DLHC-SiC/Graphene Heterojunctions

Recently, there has been extensive discovery of vertically-stacked 2D heterojunctions comprising diverse 2D materials^{51, 52}. These heterojunctions are manufactured using vdW interlayer interactions, demonstrating properties that differ from those of individual layers. For example, twisted bilayer graphene has revealed unconventional quantum Hall effects² and Van Hove singularities⁵³⁻⁵⁵. The heterostructures fabricated by the combination of graphene and SiC can be interesting for potential applications in optoelectronics and nanoelectronics^{56, 57}. Another example of SiC/graphene heterostructure are vertical heterojunctions that have been successfully fabricated through approaches such as vdW epitaxy, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and direct growth, including MoS₂/graphene and graphene/hBN multilayer heterojunctions⁵⁸. We investigated the structural, electronic, and mechanical properties of SiC/graphene (DLHC-SiC/Gr) structures with first-principle calculations, and report the results in Figure 6. The optimized lattice parameters for graphene and DLHC-SiC, are 2.47 and 3.15 Å, respectively,⁵⁶. Constructing a heterostructure using these cells would result in a lattice mismatch of 27.53%, which is too high for

successful heterostructure formation. Therefore, a 3x3 supercell of DLHC-SiC and a 4x4 supercell of graphene were combined to reduce the mismatch, as depicted in Figure 6a. The lattice constants 3x3 DLHC-SiC supercell and a 4x4 graphene supercell are 9.45 Å and 9.88 Å, respectively, reducing the lattice mismatch of 4.55%, which is an acceptable value for heterostructure formation. After fully relaxing the heterostructure (without fixing the cell), the final structure lattice parameter becomes 9.72 Å, corresponding to 1.62% compression of graphene and a 2.86% expansion of DLHC-SiC. The exfoliation energy between graphene and SiC (XC) structures is determined as the energy difference between the single layers over the area A :

$$E_b = \frac{E_{XC/Gr} - E_{XC} - E_{Gr}}{A} \quad (2)$$

Here, $E_{XC/Gr}$ shows the total energy of the XC/graphene heterojunction, while E_{Gr} and E_{XC} correspond to the total energies of the graphene and XC layers, respectively, and A is the interface area. In Figure 6, we report the details of this heterostructure. It may be noted that the interlayer spacing (Figure 6a) is comparable in order of magnitude to other bilayer vdW heterostructures, suggesting that SiC/graphene structures conform to the characteristics of a typical vdW system⁵⁷. In Figure 6b, we report the calculated electrostatic potential as a function of separation from the heterostructure along the direction perpendicular to the layers. Three distinct peaks corresponding to each layer of the heterostructure has been identified and marked. Figure 6c shows the PBE-GGA band structure for the heterostructure. The distinct linear dispersion due to graphene is visible at high-symmetry K -point.

Figure 6. DHLC-SiC/Graphene heterostructure: (a) structure, (b) electrostatic potential of DHLC-SiC/Graphene heterostructure with dipole moment correction, and (c) electronic bands, the Fermi level at $E_F=0$ is marked with a dashed line.

Table IV. Calculated structural and mechanical properties of a graphene-SiC heterostructure: optimized in-plane lattice constants ($a = b$), vdW distance h_{vdw} , out-of-plane length, binding energy E_b , electronic properties M(metal), SM (semi-metal), elastic constant C_{ij} , Poisson's ratio, Young's modulus, in-plane stiffness C .

Heterostructures	a (Å)	h_{vdw} (Å)	h_{DLHC} (Å)	E_{GGA} (eV)	E_b (eV)	C_{11} (N/m)	C_{12} (N/m)	C_{66} (N/m)	V	Y (N/m)	C (N/m)
DLHC-SiC/Gr	9.72	3.33	2.08	SM	0.09	504.89	150.53	177.18	0.29	230	1310.84

5. Conclusion and Outlook

We presented a first principles study that predicts SiC in a double-layer honeycomb structure. With DFT calculations we find interesting mechanical properties of this double-layer system such as a very high Young's modulus of around 220 N/m, and identify it as a semiconductor material with indirect band gap.

Strain-dependent calculations of the band gap promise its strong tunability throughout the full visible spectral range. While high binding energy may not allow easy exfoliation, the growth of multilayer SiC structures on a TaC substrate following the approach of Ref. ²⁶ may provide a feasible strategy. In the future, it would be interesting to investigate band structure topologies of multilayer SiC on TaC.

Author contributions: M.F. conceived the work, performed the DFT calculations and drafted the manuscript. A.P. and S. A. performed the evolutionary structure search and strain calculations, and supervised the theoretical modeling. A.S. and R.K. coordinated the work, and all authors contributed to the writing of the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest. The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

Supplementary Information is available free of charge providing

- Low Energy structures in SiC found in evolutionary search:
- Calculated STM images, and electrostatic potential of the XC DLHC structures.
- Calculated STM images, and electrostatic potential of the XC DLHC structures.
- Calculated phonon dispersions of the DLHC SiC structure.
- Electronic properties of bilayer GeC and SnC.
- Calculated optical properties of DLHC-SiC.

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